

A Paradigm Shift In Buying Behaviour Of College Students Towards Apparel In Haryana

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Abstract

Textile industry contributes about 2% to India's GDP and market size of this industry has reached \$172.3 Billion. Export of the industry crossed \$44 Billion and contributed 10.6% in India's total exports. This data clearly shows the importance of textile industry in the growth of India's economy. And to understand the customer is the success key of any business. So, this is a review paper which critically examines the work that is already published regarding the shift in the buying behavior of students towards apparel. This paper tries to evaluate the shifts in the buying behavior of college students towards apparel.

Introduction

Customers are the people who purchase goods and services from companies or from particular stores for the purpose of business or entrepreneurial activities. In this era of globalization, customers are considered the 'king of the market'. Due to globalization customers have a wide range of products and options so they can choose the alternative which is best from them. A free-market economy is used for the customer to be fully informed and educated which can influence the market with there are rational decisions. Therefore, the decision making of the customer is of great interest for business. Business want to collect more and more information regarding customer behavior in different situations and scenarios.

Textile industry contributes about 2% in the GDP of India and market size of this industry has reached \$172.3 Billion. Export of industry crossed \$44 Billion and contributed 10.6% in India's total exports. This data clearly shows the importance of textile industry in the growth of India's economy. And to understand the customer is the success key of any business. So, this study help the companies in this sector to understand its customers and grow further, which ultimately lead the economy to grow and reach the vision of becoming a \$ 5 trillion economy.

Customer behavior is related to the study of how individual customers, families and households make decisions on how to spend their available income on consumption-related items. This includes the study of what customers buy, when they buy it, from where they buy it, how often they buy it, how often they use it, how they evaluate it after purchase, the impact of such evaluations on future purchases.

According to five-stage model of customer buying process, customer undergo the following stages while purchasing any product

1. Need recognition
2. Information search
3. Evaluation of alternatives
4. Purchase decision

5. Post purchase behaviour

Need recognition: In this step, the customer recognizes need for a product or service. In this the customer starts facing the problem that can be sold by a product or services.

Information search: In this step, after recognizing the need, customer search for information of available products and service which can be used to satisfy his/her need. It involves making a list of products and services which can be used by the customer to fulfill the requirement.

Evaluation of alternatives: After collection of information all the alternatives available they are evaluated by the customer to select the best one out of all.

Purchase decision: This is the main step, as the customer makes his/her purchase decision after evaluation of all the alternatives.

Post purchase decision: This step is post purchase decision. It involves decisions which are made by customer after purchasing the product and evaluating its performance and usage. This step is very crucial as it influence the future purchase behavior.

From past few decades customers have been undergoing a lot of transformations from passive customers to active enhancers. Customer behavior is influenced by a lot of factors that includes:

1. Psychological factors
2. Social factors
3. Cultural factors
4. Personal factors
5. Economic factors

Psychological factors are mainly concerned with

1. Perception,
2. Learning,
3. Attitude, and
4. Belief of individual

Social factors are concerned with family reference groups and rules and status.

Cultural factors are related to this set of values and ideologies which includes culture, subculture and social class.

Personal factors differ from person to person and the main influential factor in buying behavior of individual. Personal factor includes age of a person occupation of a person income and lifestyle of a person.

Economic factor influences customer behavior as it includes family income, personal income, liquid assets, saving, etc.

Consumers are someone OR group of people who purchased goods from a particular store for self consumption or for their family for the purpose of use. The purpose of consumer to buy goods and services is not to earn income, manufacturing and for resale. Consumers are the 'king of market'.

Consumer Behavior Towards Online Shopping

Online Shopping is increased day-by-day due to spreading of internet facilities, convenience in shopping, availability of variety of products at low price, increasing income level and standard of living, changing in taste and preferences etc. The attitude of consumers change towards online shopping it is directly related with income level of consumers. If income of consumers increased the positive attitude of consumers towards online shopping also increased. On the otherside, if income level of consumers decreased the positive attitude of consumers towards online shopping also decreased. Consumers can buy product online at any time 24*7 very easily without incurred any transportation cost.

During Covid-19 Government imposed restrictions on travelling or in outdoor activities for decreasing the impact of spreading corona virus. At that time, consumers buy necessity products online due to fear of corona virus and several restrictions imposed by government.

In Online Shopping several retail stores provides return policy of goods to their consumers. So, interest of consumers increased towards online shopping. Companies can also conveys information to their buyers, timely takes feedback. Companies also gives timely several discount to their customers for increasing the demand of their products.

Online Shopping also increased due to cheap 4G network. Consumers use internet not only for buying products and services. Service includes Airline Ticket, Hotel Room etc. But they compare prices of product, features of product and after sale services which are to be provided by e- stores to their customers. Online shopping integrates the economy with rest of the world by expanding business globally. Due to globalization consumers have variety of products available for consumption.

Apparel

Apparel is the term which is used for clothing. Apparel includes readymade garments which are wear casually or on special occasion and it is further categorized according to Brand, Age Group, Price and Styles. Apparel also categorized into Men Apparel, Women Apparel and Kids Apparel.

Women's Apparel includes apparel which is worn by women. Types of Women Apparel

1. Bridal
2. Evening Wear
3. Active Wear includes jogging, running
4. Double ticket sizing
5. Dresses
6. T-Shirt
7. Sweater
8. Shorts
9. Jeans
10. Suit

Men's Apparel includes apparel which is worn by men. Types of Men Apparel

1. Sweater
2. Shirt
3. Jeans
4. Gloves
5. Cap
6. Blazer
7. Shorts
8. Lower
9. Coat
10. Indo western

Children's Apparel includes apparel which is worn by kids. Types of Kids Apparel

1. T-Shirts
2. Denim
3. Trousers
4. Skirts
5. Frock
6. Jeans
7. Jacket
8. Coat
9. Shirt

In today's era, consumer can demand affordable best branded product by comparing different brands products it is possible due to technological advancement. People can compare products on the basis of price, brand, trend etc.

Apparel includes stitched, semi-stitched and unstitched clothes. Examples- unstitched suits and shirts, t-shirts, jump suits, western dresses, coat etc. Many factors which influence the buying behavior of consumers specially Gender. Gender is one of the major influencing factors which change the buying behavior of men and women. The needs and the behavior of men and women are different.

Demand of any products depends upon income of consumer, if income of consumer high then they can demand branded products and if income of consumer is low, then they can demand those products whose range is nominal and according to their requirements.

Review Of Literature

1) Singh, Nirbhan And Sarvanan, R (2013) In His Research Paper Whose Headed Is "A Comprehensive Study On Female Buying Behaviour For Apparel Segment In Coimbatore" The objective of researcher is to know the buying behavior of females towards apparel, to find out those factors which affects the behavior of females while purchasing and knows the preference of females in clothing like fabric, fashion and brand etc. The research is based on primary data and data is collected through questionnaire and personal meeting of 300 female consumers of middle age group 15-45. The research is restricted only Coimbatore urban area women like college girls, working and non-working women. Researcher should found in his research there are lot of factors involves in buying behavior of women while they are shopping and its impact on its geographical area. Researcher should found women mostly purchase apparel on any festival & on special occasion for looking good and availability of many discounts and offers etc. Researcher also finds apparel is an important part of every women and it can enhance the confidence level and self-respect of women. Women puts all efforts in seeking their required product. Most of the women purchased branded clothes, clothes which are in trend and after seeking

many qualities in clothes. All these factors helps the women in choosing clothes according to their preference, tradition and culture.

2) Chakrapani, A.(2015) Tried To Study "The Consumer Behavior And Preferences Of Indian Consumers Towards Apparel Purchase In Retail Markets In India". The purpose of the study was to understand the drivers of consumer behavior in India, especially among 15-20 & 21-25 year olds. Also, to analyze the preference of Indian consumers towards branded, non-branded and western wears. The survey was conducted in 4 cities- Delhi NCR, Gurgaon, Ghaziabad, Faridabad and Noida. The Research was primary in nature and done through a designing questionnaire of 200 respondents- 100 males & 100 females. This questionnaire was communicated to respondents via social network, online links to consumer working in various companies. The study was revealed that the consumer whose age between 15-20 years purchase less product than the consumer whose age between 21-25 years because of financial independence of late stage respondents. Consumers of the age institution 15-20 who're the pioneers of subsequent technology have been inquisitive about western clothing and that has led to say no in conventional put on in India. The surveyed age institution of 15-20 turned into very precise approximately the manufacturers and that they judged manufacturers primarily based totally on perceived quality, fee for cash and availability of variety of apparels.

3) Kasuma, J, Et.Al (2015) Made A Study On "Finding Out The Determinants For The Purchase Of Luxury Handbags Amongst The Youth" The objective of the study was to finds relationship between determinants, mainly economic, functional, personal, social value and buyer's purchase intentions. The study population was Generation Y, aged 20-38, living in Kuching, Sarawak. A convenient sampling method was used for data collection of the 384 questionnaires distributed to the target group, only 200 were returned, most of them were female. Collected data were tested using methods of correlation and regression analysis via the Social Sciences version 20 statistical package. The study found that all the determinants considered in the hypothesis were strongly associated with Generation Y intention to purchase luxury handbags.

4) Reddy, N.H & Srinivas (2015) in their research studied that online shopping is increasing day-by-day in the field of e-business. E-business helps the people in buying product inside the world. Many entrepreneurs runs their on-line portals to enhance their product on-line by providing different services to buyers. On-line buying is famous inside the advanced countries, its enlargement inside the Indian marketplace. However, internet penetration is

very high degree in India because of cheaper tax, better bandwidth facilities and less expensive hardware. Researcher should use Qualitative and Quantitative research methods in their research to know the impact of Demographic factors (age, population, gender) etc. on Indian consumers buying behavior. After thorough study, researcher should find demographic factors like marital status, size of family, gender, age, level of income & education of consumers have substantially influencing online shopping. The Researcher may want to use the outcomes in their examine for carrying out destiny research on this area.

5) Dr. Paliwal, L.R And Bansal, Aishvarya (2017) In Their Research Paper “ **A Study Of Young Consumer Behaviour Towards Branded Apparel**” observed the behaviour of Delhi & NCR young consumer towards apparel and how much income they can spend on branded apparel. The research is descriptive in nature examined the behaviour of consumer towards apparel is positive or not. Researcher should collect information from both Primary as well as Secondary source by formulating Questionnaire using multiple grid, likert scale and MCQs of 200 young consumers including both males & females. These consumers are differentiated according to profession, job, business and age. Samples were taken randomly from area of Delhi & NCR and according to their convenience. The result of study is based on demographic profile of consumer. The market of young consumer are wide in range and rapidly increasing due to awareness of young consumers towards branded apparels. After thorough study, researcher should find and conclude that there is positive attitude of both male and female towards branded apparel and further they buy branded apparel fulfilling their want, need, for the purpose of gifting and for social status etc. Some of consumer purchased branded apparel followed by family and friends due to followed by family and friends many of consumer shifts another brand apparel and try some new and different brand apparel. Some of consumer don't buy branded apparel due to financial crisis so, income also plays a vital role in choosing branded apparel and some of students depends on their parental income for purchasing some branded goods so, family plays a significant role in purchasing some branded goods. Thus, marketer's should make a strategy bringing more loyalty among young consumer towards brand for avoiding brand shifting.

6) Dhiman, R., Chand, P. K., & Gupta, S. (2018) in their research article whose title is “**Behavioural Aspects Influencing Decision to Purchase Apparels amongst Young Indian Consumers**” The main purpose of researcher is to know the behavior of consumers towards apparel.

Researcher should create huge attempt to differentiate among variables which have an effect on the selection of apparel purchased amongst youth. The research is based on secondary data means data is collected through various journals, research paper, articles, magazines etc. those which are related to consumer buying behavior. Confirmatory issue evaluation is achieved to extract elements which have an effect on the purchaser shopping for behavior and sooner or later buy decision. Total of six influential elements extracted from 20 widely recognized indicators. After depth study researcher should find that client buy conduct in branded apparel along with occurrence buy conduct, a mean of the spending, desired keep class and desired logo particularly relies upon on plenty of demographic variables. The researcher should examine that every domestic and global manufacturers are selling their products in Indian market and are bought by the purchasers so long as the ones are determined to distribute fee to purchasers.

7) Kushwah, Vigg, Silky And Singh, Anjali (2019) was conduct a research paper. The purpose of conducting research paper to know the behavior of middle class educated consumers towards Online Shopping. In her study it consist a study of factorial. The researcher takes some objective to overcome their problem the objectives are- Develop and standardize measures to evaluate customer behavior with respect to Online shopping, To analyze the current purchasing pattern of middle class educated consumers of urban area, explore the main underlying factors induce customers to shop online, Open new research areas. For their study, Data collected by a sample of 400 educated middle class consumers from urban area. The paper consists a study of factorial and they select consumers according to the non-probability sampling OR using an intentional sampling technique. The study discovered that this consumer behavior is implemented by three main factors such as the image of the seller, the quality of the website and the worry of the seller for the customer. Researcher should find “We discover that the perception of the privacy protection factor was high for the websites most commonly used by consumers and emerged as the most important factor that led to online purchases. The study concludes that with the probability of change in shopping behavior from traditional to continuous virtual and accelerated virtual one, 2 Journal of General Management Research Marketers will have to withdraw them in their distribution and promotional models in order to face the new challenges changed behavior of the customer.

Conclusion

From the analysis of previous research work, it is concluded that most of the women consumer prefer branded product. The demographic profile of consumer also affects the buying behavior of consumer i.e, culture, tradition and preference. The research has also revealed that buying behavior of consumer is influenced by seller's image, quality of the website and sellers concern for their consumers. Research has been found out that income is an important factor which influences the consumer buying behavior. Age group between 15-20 purchase less product than the age of 21-25 because of financial dependence on their parents.

Thus, Sellers's should makes strategy bringing more loyalty among consumers towards brand and marketer also focus on the market profile and the brand loyalty so, the consumer do not shift on another brand.

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